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A STUDY OF PERFORMANCE OF MUTUAL FUNDS IN A SELECTED EQUITY & DEBT SCHEMES

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Abstract

In the post reform era, private sector mutual funds started participating actively in the Indian mutual fund industry. Consequently, large number of investment schemes launched by different asset management companies surfaced out. The selection criteria of mutual fund became more complex in context of accommodating both return and risk measurement. For this reason fund managers are more concerned to retain investors' confidence. Objective of this paper is to judge and compare the performance of selected equity and debt oriented mutual fund schemes with the help of important models based on risk- return relationship.

JEL Classification: G11, G23

Key Words: Mutual Funds, NAV, Risk-return, Beta, Co-efficient of determination.

Introduction

With the rapid growth of Indian capital market, investments in financial assets also increased rapidly. In the past, investors (particularly small investors) had limited investment options e.g. shares, bonds and debentures, post office deposits, and bank FDs etc. But in recent times investors have got lot more avenues for this purpose and mutual funds are one of them. According to Weston J Fred and Brigham, Eugene, F 'Mutual funds are corporations which accept dollars to buy stocks, long term bond, short term debt instruments issued by business or Government Units, These corporations pool fund and thus reduce risk by diversification'. So it is one of the preferred investment avenues for investors as it provides the opportunity to invest in a professionally managed and well-diversified

portfolio. In the post economic reform period, a new picture emerged in the Indian mutual fund industry-viz. the entry of private sector mutual funds. Consequently a large number of mutual funds with even larger number of schemes surfaced out. Against this backdrop, the investors are concerned about choice criteria of the funds. Evaluation of past performance is crucial for both the investors and the fund managers. Proper evaluation help the investors to decide the level of investment in various schemes by estimating the amount of return that has been generated by the fund and the level of risk associated with it over a period of time. It enables the fund managers to identify strengths and weaknesses of these schemes which help them to take improved decisions in future.

This research paper is an attempt to compare the performance of equity and debt oriented mutual fund schemes and help investors and mutual fund companies to have an idea about the investment style and performance of mutual funds in Indian.

Theoretically equity oriented mutual fund mainly invests in high growth equity share and other equity related instruments. This type of fund is ideal for the investor who have long term outlook seeking growth over a period of time. Debt oriented mutual fund invests in fixed income securities like debentures, bonds, money market instruments etc. and it provides regular income to the investors. Generally speaking, equity funds are considered to be riskier in comparison to debt based funds.

Review of Literature

Majority of the research work in the field of mutual funds have been carried out in the industrialised countries. However, there are many studies which have been conducted in India as well. Notable contributors among them are Madhu S. Panigrahi (1996), Sathya Swaroop Debasish (2009), Sarika Keswani (2011), Vikas Kumar (2011), Bhaskar Goswami and Sharmistha Acharyya (2012) and Bhaskar Goswami (2012). Madhu S. Panigrahi (1996) analyses the reason behind the attractiveness of mutual funds in last few years and attributed it to its fastest growth, good performance, skilled manpower and its quicker spreadness to the relatively wider area than equity in recent years.

Sathya Swaroop debasish (2009) analyses the performance based on mean return, beta, Sharpe's ratio, Treynor's ratio, and Jensen's alpha of 23 equity based mutual funds offered by six private sectors and three public sectors mutual fund companies. Sarika Keswani (2011) empirically examined the effect of fund size on the performance of open ended balanced mutual funds in India. Vikas Kumar (2011) studied the performance of 20 open ended schemes which are launched by five private sector mutual fund companies. Bhaskar Goswami and Sharmistha Acharyya (2012) presented in detail the descriptive overview of various mutual fund schemes and its relative importance in the Indian financial sector. Bhaskar Goswami (2012) studied and presented the financial performance of selected mutual fund schemes.

Objectives

In contrast to existing literature, this study focuses on following objectives:

1. To examine the performance of selected mutual funds in terms of Sharpe, Treynor, Jensen and Fama's measures.
2. To ascertain the degree by which the market index explains the volatility of the return of portfolio of various funds.

Data and Its Source

A total of 34 mutual fund schemes have been selected for the purpose of this study with equal proportion of equity and debt oriented schemes, that is, 17 are equity based schemes and rest of schemes are debt oriented. These schemes are chosen from 4 private sector mutual fund companies namely Birla Sun Life Mutual Fund, HDFC Mutual Fund, ICICI Prudential Mutual Fund, and Reliance Mutual Fund and 2 public sector mutual fund companies namely UTI Mutual Fund and SBI Mutual Fund. Annually adjusted data of net asset value (NAV) have been collected from 1999 to 2011 from capital line database. The source of daily Sensex (market index) and 91 days Treasury bill rate of return (risk free rate of return) is capital line database only.

Methodology

Following research methodology has been used in the present study:

Return

The returns are worked out on the basis of NAV of different schemes. The return of a mutual fund scheme (R_{pt}) at time t is as follows:

$$R_{pt} = \frac{NAV_t - NAV_{t-1}}{NAV_{t-1}} \tag{1}$$

Here NAV_t and NAV_{t-1} are the net asset value for the time period t and t-1 respectively. The average return of each mutual fund scheme (R_p^*) over the study period is as follow

$$R_p^* = \sum_{t=1}^n \frac{R_{pt}}{n} \tag{2}$$

Here R_{pt} is the return of mutual fund scheme at time t and n is the total number of year studied.

Risk Free Rate

Risk free rate of return is defined as the return on investment which has no risk associated with it. For the study it has been taken as the average return on 91 days treasury bill during the period of study (7%).

Benchmark Index

In this study, BSE Sensex is used as benchmark index or market index. Return of market index is computed on the basis of BSE Sensex on the respective data.

Risk

Risk is measured by the following statistical tools such as standard deviation, beta etc.

Standard Deviation (Std. Dev.)

$$\sigma_p = \sqrt{\frac{\sum (R_p - R_p^*)^2}{n-1}} \tag{3}$$

Where R_p = Return on fund portfolio
 R_p^* = Average return on fund portfolio

Beta

Beta co-efficient is an indicator of systematic risk of the portfolio of each mutual fund scheme. It is used for evaluation of fund's volatility as regard to market index and measurement the extent of co-movement of fund with that of market index. Beta (β) co-efficient can be calculated as –

$$\beta = \frac{COV(p,m)}{\sigma_m^2} \tag{4}$$

Where $COV(p,m)$ = Covariance between return of fund and market index.
 σ_m = Standard deviation of market index

Coefficient of Determination

Coefficient of determination (r^2) indicates the extent to which the movement of fund can be explained by corresponding market index. It also a diversification index of fund portfolio. Higher the value of r^2 (close to 1) indicates higher portfolio diversification and vice versa. The coefficient of determination can be estimated by regressing each fund scheme return as against the market return.

Sharpe's Ratio

Sharpe's Ratio (Si) is defined as –

$$Si = \frac{R_p^* - R_f}{\sigma_p} \tag{5}$$

Where R_p^* = Average return of fund

R_f = Risk free rate of return

σ_p = Standard deviation of return of fund

Treynor's Index

Treynor's Index (Ti) is given

$$Ti = \frac{R_p^* - R_f}{\beta_p} \tag{6}$$

Where R_p^* = Average return of fund

R_f = Risk free rate of return

β_p = Sensitivity of fund return to market return

Jensen's Alpha

Jensen's alpha (α) is based on capital asset pricing model. Positive alpha indicates good performance. It is expressed as –

$$\alpha = R_p^* - R_f - \beta_p * (R_m^* - R_f) \tag{7}$$

Where R_p^* = Average return of fund portfolio

R_f = Risk free rate of return

β_p = Sensitivity of fund return to market return

R_m^* = Average return of market portfolio

Fama's Measure (FM)

Eugene Fama provides a framework to measure performance of a fund. Total return of a fund portfolio is divided into four components as- (1) risk free return (2) return from bearing systematic risk (3) compensation for inadequate diversification (4) return from fund selection. Net selectivity is the excess return adjusted for all risk. The fund manager can choose undervalued securities to earn greater return which is determined by the following formula –

$$FM = (R_p^* - R_f) - \left(\frac{\sigma_p}{\sigma_m}\right) * (R_m^* - R_f) \tag{8}$$

Where R_p^* = Average return of fund portfolio

R_f = Risk free rate of return

σ_p = Standard deviation of portfolio return

σ_m = Standard deviation of market index

R_m^* = Average return of market portfolio

Findings and Observation

Table No. 1: Mean Return, Standard deviation, Beta and Co-efficient of Determination

Name of scheme	Mean	Std. Dev.	Beta	r ²
Equity Schemes				
Birla Sun Life Advantage Fund (D)	0.18	0.52	1.11	0.94
Birla Sun Life Equity Fund (G)	0.26	0.53	1.13	0.93
Birla Sun Life India Opportunities Fund - B (G)	0.15	0.50	1.03	0.88

HDFC Equity Fund - (G)	0.30	0.52	1.10	0.92
HDFC Top 200 Fund (G)	0.28	0.53	1.11	0.9
HDFC Tax Saver Fund (D)	0.32	0.49	1.02	0.87
ICICI Pru Top 200 Fund - (G)	0.25	0.52	1.10	0.93
ICICI Pru Tax Plan - (G)	0.29	0.60	1.23	0.86
ICICI Pru FMCG Fund - (G)	0.23	0.40	0.74	0.72
Reliance Growth Fund - (G)	0.35	0.62	1.26	0.85
Reliance Vision Fund - (G)	0.32	0.58	1.12	0.77
SBI Magnum Equity Fund (D)	0.19	0.54	1.15	0.94
SBI Magnum Tax Gain Scheme (D)	0.26	0.62	1.26	0.85
SBI Magnum SFU - FMCG Fund	0.17	0.38	0.71	0.73
UTI-Mastershare (G)	0.18	0.41	0.88	0.95
UTI-Energy Fund (D)	0.31	0.51	0.83	0.54
UTI-Pharma & Healthcare Fund (G)	0.12	0.29	0.57	0.77
Debt Schemes				
Birla Sun Life Income Plus - Retail (Div-Q)	0.09	0.07	-0.10	0.38
Birla Sun Life Income Plus - Retail (G)	0.09	0.08	-0.11	0.41
Birla Sun Life Short Term Fund (G)	0.09	0.08	-0.12	0.45
Birla Sun Life Cash Plus - Inst (Div-D)	0.08	0.07	-0.04	0.61
HDFC High Interest Fund (G)	0.08	0.07	-0.10	0.43
HDFC High Interest Fund (Qtly Div)	0.08	0.07	-0.10	0.44
ICICI Pru Income Plan - (G)	0.09	0.07	-0.11	0.43
ICICI Pru Gilt Fund - Treasury (G)	0.08	0.05	-0.07	0.44
Reliance Income Fund - (Div-A)	0.08	0.06	-0.08	0.38
Reliance Income Fund - (Div-HY)	0.08	0.06	-0.08	0.33
Reliance Income Fund - (Div-M)	0.08	0.06	-0.09	0.39
Reliance Income Fund - (Div-Q)	0.08	0.06	-0.09	0.4
Reliance Income Fund - (G)	0.09	0.06	-0.10	0.47
SBI Magnum InstaCash - Cash Plan	0.07	0.02	-0.03	0.57
UTI-Treasury Advantage Fund (Div-Q)	0.08	0.05	-0.04	0.17
UTI-Treasury Advantage Fund (G)	0.08	0.05	-0.04	0.17
UTI-Money Market Fund (G)	0.07	0.02	-0.03	0.5
Market index	0.17	0.42		

Source: Capital line database

Table 1 represents average return, standard deviation, beta and co-efficient of determination (r^2) of the selected equity and debt oriented mutual fund schemes.

In case of equity oriented schemes Reliance Growth Fund-(G) has highest mean return of 35% followed by Reliance Vision Fund (G) - 32%, HDFC Tax Savers Fund (D) and HDFC Equity Fund (G) - 30%. Out of the 17 equity oriented schemes only 2 schemes, namely Birla Sun Life India Opportunities Fund - B (G) and UTI - Pharma and Healthcare Fund (G) have return less than BSE Sensex market index (0.17). It could be seen from the table that all debt oriented mutual fund schemes underperform market index. Out of 17 schemes, 5 schemes namely Birla Sun Life Income Plus - Retail (Div-Q), Birla Sun Life Income Plus - Retail (G), Birla Sun Life Short Term Fund (G), ICICI

Pru Income Plan - (G) and ICICI Pru Income Plan - (G) earned average return of 9%. Rest of 12 fund scheme have return within the range 7% to 8%.

3rd column of the above table indicates the standard deviation of fund return. Standard deviation measures the volatility of fund return in the market. As per the theoretical characteristics of equity based mutual fund, almost all fund schemes proved to be highly volatile. Maximum standard deviation is shown in Reliance Growth Fund (G) and SBI Magnum Tax Gain Scheme (D) i.e. 0.62. Only 4 schemes i.e. ICICI Prudential FMCG Fund (G), SBI Magnum SFU - FMCG Fund, UTI Mastershare (G) and UTI Pharma and Healthcare Fund (G) are less volatile than market index. Debt oriented mutual fund schemes are less risky than market index. Birla Sun Life Income Plus - Retail (G) and Birla Sun Life Short Term Fund (G) have highest standard deviation which is .08. SBI Magnum InstaCash - Cash Plan has lowest standard deviation. Low standard deviation is a signal of little fluctuation in return.

Beta value expresses systematic risk or aggressiveness of fund return. Table 1 points out that out of the 17 schemes, 12 have beta value greater than one which signifies that these schemes tend to hold portfolios that are more risky than market portfolio. Among these 12 aggressive schemes, 10 belong to the private sector mutual funds and interestingly 2 schemes falls under the domain of public sector mutual fund (SBI Magnum Equity Fund (D) and SBI Magnum Tax Gain Scheme (D)). Beta values of debt oriented mutual fund schemes are negative and less than 1 that is these funds are less risky in market.

Last column of table 1 shows the values of co-efficient of determination or r^2 . From the table it can be concluded that equity oriented fund schemes are highly diversified. UTI-Mastershare (G) has highest value of r^2 (95%) followed by SBI Magnum Equity Fund (D) (94%). R^2 value lies within the range 0.75 to 0.95. Co-efficient of determination of debt oriented mutual fund schemes lies within the range 0.17 to 0.61. So equity oriented funds are more diversified than debt oriented fund in this study period. r^2 value of equity oriented fund schemes suggest that market can easily explain the substantial part of the variation in return of a particular scheme while in case of debt oriented fund it is hard to do that.

Table No. 2: Sharpe's Ratio, Treynor's Index, Jensen's Alpha and Fama's Measure

Name of scheme	Sharpe ratio	Treynor's Index	Jensen's Alpha	Fama's Measure
Equity Schemes				
Birla Sun Life Advantage Fund (D)	0.2185	0.1022	-0.0017	-0.0161
Birla Sun Life Equity Fund (G)	0.3554	0.1670	0.0715	0.0563
Birla Sun Life India Opportunities Fund – B (G)	0.1674	0.0806	-0.0239	-0.0406
HDFC Equity Fund – (G)	0.4512	0.2128	0.1202	0.1049
HDFC Top 200 Fund (G)	0.3923	0.1882	0.0941	0.0764
HDFC Tax Saver Fund (D)	0.5022	0.2440	0.1424	0.1247
ICICI Pru Top 200 Fund – (G)	0.3399	0.1604	0.0623	0.0470
ICICI Pru Tax Plan – (G)	0.3628	0.1776	0.0907	0.0682
ICICI Pru FMCG Fund – (G)	0.3980	0.2128	0.0805	0.0587
Reliance Growth Fund – (G)	0.4436	0.2187	0.1449	0.1207
Reliance Vision Fund – (G)	0.4343	0.2249	0.1355	0.1071
SBI Magnum Equity Fund (D)	0.2162	0.1013	-0.0029	-0.0180
SBI Magnum Tax Gain Scheme (D)	0.3145	0.1544	0.0637	0.0402
SBI Magnum SFU – FMCG Fund	0.2552	0.1352	0.0225	0.0022
UTI-Mastershare (G)	0.2700	0.1259	0.0194	0.0084
UTI-Energy Fund (D)	0.4659	0.2866	0.1516	0.1104
UTI-Pharma & Healthcare Fund (G)	0.1837	0.0947	-0.0051	-0.0192

Debt Schemes				
Birla Sun Life Income Plus – Retail (Div-Q)	0.2092	-0.1533	0.0252	-0.0029
Birla Sun Life Income Plus – Retail (G)	0.2631	-0.1872	0.0311	0.0010
Birla Sun Life Short Term Fund (G)	0.2572	-0.1734	0.0322	0.0006
Birla Sun Life Cash Plus – Inst (Div-D)	0.2243	-0.4109	0.0185	-0.0016
HDFC High Interest Fund (G)	0.1604	-0.1107	0.0211	-0.0060
HDFC High Interest Fund (Qtly Div)	0.1099	-0.0752	0.0173	-0.0092
ICICI Pru Income Plan – (G)	0.2679	-0.1853	0.0308	0.0014
ICICI Pru Gilt Fund – Treasury (G)	0.2414	-0.1661	0.0192	-0.0004
Reliance Income Fund – (Div-A)	0.2351	-0.1726	0.0233	-0.0009
Reliance Income Fund – (Div-HY)	0.1653	-0.1296	0.0186	-0.0053
Reliance Income Fund – (Div-M)	0.1613	-0.1177	0.0191	-0.0055
Reliance Income Fund – (Div-Q)	0.1763	-0.1261	0.0201	-0.0046
Reliance Income Fund – (G)	0.2692	-0.1791	0.0269	0.0012
SBI Magnum InstaCash - Cash Plan	-0.1422	0.0856	0.0005	-0.0066
UTI-Treasury Advantage Fund (Div-Q)	0.1294	-0.1398	0.0104	-0.0055
UTI-Treasury Advantage Fund (G)	0.2109	-0.2341	0.0152	-0.0019
UTI-Money Market Fund (G)	-0.0656	0.0420	0.0018	-0.0058
Market index	0.2494			

Source: Capital line database

Table 2 compares the performance of equity and debt oriented mutual fund schemes with the help of different measures given by Sharpe, Treynor, Jensen and Fama.

Sharpe's measure is defined as the average return generated by the fund over and above risk free rate of return and total risk associated with it. High positive values of this measure imply better performance. Out of 34 selected mutual fund schemes, 13 equity oriented fund and 4 debt oriented fund have recorded better Sharpe ratio than market index (0.2494). Among equity schemes, HDFC Tax Savers Fund (D) has highest Sharpe ratio (0.5022) followed by UTI Energy Fund (0.4436). Birla Sun Life India Opportunity fund has lowest Sharpe ratio followed by UTI Pharma & Healthcare fund (G). In debt schemes Reliance Income Fund (G) has highest Sharpe ratio followed by ICICI Pru Income Plan (G) (0.2679), Birla Sun Life Income Plus – Retail (G) (0.2631). Two debt oriented scheme namely SBI Magnum InstaCash - Cash Plan and UTI-Money Market Fund (G) have negative Sharpe ratio.

Treynor's index is the excess return over risk free rate of return per unit of systematic risk. Among equity schemes with respect to Treynor's index, satisfactory results are shown by UTI Energy Fund (0.2866), HDFC Tax Saver Fund (D) (0.2440) and Reliance Vision Fund. Treynor's index of 16 debt oriented fund scheme are found to be negative not because of poor performance but because of negative beta value. In absolute term Birla Sun Life Cash Plus – Inst (Div-D) has highest Treynor's index followed by Birla Sun Life Income Plus – Retail (G) and ICICI Pru Income Plan – (G). Two schemes namely SBI Magnum InstaCash - Cash Plan and UTI Money market fund which have positive Treynor's index are the poor performers. For these schemes positive value arises due to ratio of two negative values (one is beta and other is the difference between excess return and risk free rate of return).

Greater positive values of Jensen's alpha indicate good performance of funds and better market timing ability of fund manager as regard to investment in securities. 13 out of 17 equity based mutual fund schemes have positive values of Jensen's alpha. Out of those 13 mutual fund schemes UTI Energy fund – (D) has largest value of Jensen's alpha (0.1516) followed by Reliance Growth Fund – (G) (0.1449) and HDFC Tax savers Fund – (D) (0.1424). All debt oriented scheme have positive Jensen's alpha. Highest value of alpha obtained by Birla Sun Life Short term fund – (G) (0.0322)

followed by Birla Sun Life Income plus Retail (G) (0.0311) and ICICI Prudential Income Plan (G) (0.0308).

Result of Fama's selectivity measure of the mutual fund schemes are depicted in the last column of Table 2. More or less all the fund schemes except few (UTI Pharma & Healthcare Fund (G), SBI Magnum Equity Fund (D) and Birla Sun Life India Opportunity Fund (D)) have positive Fama's measure. Opposite results are shown in debt oriented mutual funds. Only 4 schemes (Birla Sun Life Short term fund (G), Birla Sun Life Income Plus Retail (G), ICICI Prudential Income Plan (G) and Reliance Income Plan (G)) have positive value of Fama's measure. Rest of the schemes are poor performers according to Fama's measure.

Table No.3: Overall Comparison

Fund Type	Mean	Std. Dev.	Beta	r ²	Sharpe's Ratio	Treynor's Index	Jensen's Alpha	Fama's Measure
Equity	good	high	high	high	good	good	good	good
Debt	average	low	low	average	good	good	good	poor

Conclusion

It is quite evident from the analysis that selected fund schemes performed quite well in the study period. Table 3 compares equity and debt oriented schemes as a whole. This study points out that equity oriented funds generated better return in comparison to the debt oriented funds but at the same time these schemes were more volatile than the debt oriented schemes. Coefficient of determination (r²) values of all equity oriented funds are greater than the same of the debt oriented funds. Comparison on the basis of different measures i.e. Sharpe's Ratio, Treynor's Ratio, Jensen's measure and Fama's measure is as follows. Among equity schemes, UTI Energy Fund, HDFC Tax Savers Fund, Reliance Growth Fund and Reliance Vision Fund are better performers, while UTI Pharma and Healthcare Fund, SBI Magnum Equity Fund are poor performers. As far as the debt schemes are concerned, Birla Sun Life Short term fund (G), Birla Sun Life Income Plus Retail (G), ICICI Prudential Income Plan (G) and Reliance Income Plan (G) stand out as better performers.

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